

Efficacy of Environmental Hygiene Intervention Programme among Selected Women in Tamil Nadu

J. Vidhya, Assistant Professor, Department of Home Science- Interior Design & Décor
Shri Shankarlal Sundarbai Shasun Jain College for Women, Chennai – 600042.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6888-7961>

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Abstract

In India, personal hygienic environment and sanitation facilities are the top priorities of the community to develop in the rural population. Nevertheless, the aforementioned priorities need to be improved for the substantial promotion of each family's growth. This goal cannot be met without the full participation of women in the rural community. There remains a gap in the assessment of hygienic literacy, practices, and effectiveness in the implementation of hygienic environments in rural areas. The present study aimed to assess the level of awareness, attitude, and practice of environmental hygiene toward the achievement of good environmental hygiene. 500 families were selected at Eazhunagarkudiruppu, Kallukkatti, and Chengalpattu in Tamil Nadu. These rural areas are assessed to identify the effectiveness of environmental hygiene through the interview cum observation method as a tool among the select women of these places. A five-day intensive environmental hygienic programme was conducted for the selected participants. Various parameters including demographic profile, comparison, and relationship with hygienic knowledge, attitude, and practice before and after the education programme were also evaluated. Finally, it is observed that the people in rural areas lack environmental hygienic practices. The study concluded that awareness programmes are the most influential factor and have a significant and positive relationship with the development of environmental hygiene. Thus, the awareness programme and related education services towards proper and good sanitation practices are a vital need to promote a hygienic environment among women. The programme "Intervention – Creating Awareness on Environmental Hygiene" helped to identify the lack and to make sustainable solutions to raise awareness of environmental hygiene.

Keywords: Environment Hygiene, Education, Efficacy, SDG, Women, Tamil Nadu.

Introduction

The environment encompasses all elements, conditions, and factors surrounding an organism or group of organisms that can affect their development, operation, survival, and health (MedicineNet, 2021). In the context of environmental health, the term "environment" refers to external factors such as biological, physical, social, and cultural elements that may have an impact on human health. Environmental health corresponds to the discipline of public health that evaluates and monitors the interrelationship between humans and the environment to manage and mitigate factors that may affect human health. Human welfare and health can be promoted to aid in the development of secure, healthy, and hygienic societies through coordinated efforts. In the majority of rural areas of India, solid refuse is

collected and transported in an unhygienic manner. The Indian government is actively addressing the problem of solid waste management (Parmar and Pamnani, pp. 890) even though the majority of its citizens live in destitution. They are exposed to an unhealthy environment, external threats, and severe climatic conditions in succession. As people spend the majority of their time at home, housing sanitation is a top priority for public health initiatives, as it is essential for multiple dimensions of health and well-being. In rural areas, the number of household members hurts latrine usage and accessibility; this is also dependent on the education level of the household chief, his or her age, and gender. Access to and availability of water also determines access to latrines. (Indranil De, p. 652) WHO states that the housing of high quality is essential for a flourishing community. Inadequate housing is associated with infectious diseases (such as tuberculosis), stress, and depression, among other health issues. Everyone should have access to high-quality accommodation and a domestic environment that promotes happiness and contentment. Specific aspects of housing quality include ventilation, illumination, general hygiene, overcrowding, etc. Hygiene at the level of the community's good health, according to the World Health Organisation (WHO), and UNICEF (2010) is not just the absence of disease.

Review of Literature

Rakshna, M. et al had done a study on the knowledge, attitude and practices of food hygiene among school-going children aged between 11 to 15 years in Chennai, Tamil Nadu. It revealed that possible environmental awareness is needed through programmes. (Rakshna, M. et al 235)

Nath et al researched the knowledge attitude, and practices about the effects of global warming among school children aged between 11–15 years in Annai Sathya Nagar, Dharmapuri District, Tamil Nadu. They pointed out that school age is an influential stage in everyone's lives; to promote and develop sustainable health-related behaviors, as well as beliefs and attitudes. (Nath et al., 2021)

Grace et.al. points out “Menstrual hygiene practices were found to be unsatisfactory among the rural women and various restrictions during menstruation were also in practice. Women should be educated about the importance of the use of sanitary pads and the harms of using cloths. Awareness also needs to be created to abolish the unnecessary restrictions that are imposed on women to be followed during menstruation. (1734). As per the findings, women suffer from following hygienic practices and there is a need for awareness programs related to it.

Balasubramanian says “Normalization of menstruation should start from the family level and educating everyone in society including men and boys is of utmost importance. Providing choices of absorbents and the provision to change the absorbents in privacy and provision for adequate disposal of used absorbents will help reduce school absenteeism.” (65) According to him, proper awareness is important from the family itself and must be given awareness to both genders.

Lee points out there is a “lack of access to sanitation not only has negative effects on the health outcomes of women, it adversely affects their physical security and threatens the lives of children, who are most susceptible to water-borne diseases. For the rural poor, where the consequences of a lack of sanitation are most acute for women, increasing latrine provision is more strongly associated with changes in radio ownership; for the non-poor

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television ownership has a stronger relationship.” They also pin-pointed “the role of mass media in latrine ownership, and differentiating by gender, this study identifies an important mechanism that has been given less consideration in the study of women and access to basic services.” (203) The researcher pointed out that there is a lack among rural women on sanitation methods. It is suggested that mass media helps to solve these issues in the rural areas.

Singh et.al. investigated that “there have been recent initiatives by central and state governments to improve access to hygienic menstrual products, many of these programs remain in the pilot phase or are limited to certain areas.” They added, “Therefore, it is crucial to expand these initiatives to reach as many underserved individuals as possible. Additionally, governments must acknowledge the micro-level (district) disparities in the use of hygienic menstrual methods among urban women and focus on specific geographies highlighted in this study.” (17) Singh et.al. has done an extensive study to find out possible solutions from the side of the governments. They pointed out state and national governments are working together to solve these problems related to hygiene through awareness-oriented programmes.

In Tamil culture, cleanliness and environmental hygiene is very important. The people followed it promptly in every home but in the modern days, Tamil society has many pitfalls in cleanliness and environmental hygiene. In Tamil Literature, many evidences consider women as divine and known for their cleanliness and hygiene. So, environmental hygiene was present in the ancient times. A song from “Pattinapalai” states that women should be revered. Parimala pointed out the lines from the ancient Tamil work “Pattinapalai” to point out the glorified state of women.

Ongu varai Maruthin Nunthathu Uraikum

Janthal Am Nudupin Kavikulai Anna,

Serithodi Munkai Koopi Selven

Veriya Aadu Magalirodu seriyata... (Pattinapalai, L. 151-155)

The lines state that the women of that time are revered by men. Today, women encounter lots of problems related to hygienic issues. Very importantly, environmental hygiene troubles them more. The women of the rural areas, the semi-urban areas and the slums in the cities face many problems related to toilets, and personal hygiene and suffer from physical and psychological problems. Even in the times of modern AI, they suffer more and need more environmental awareness programmes to alert them to these issues. Hence, the study has been carried out to sort out the problems faced by women.

Materials and Methods

A programme “Intervention – Creating Awareness on Environmental Hygiene” was conducted on 500 households, all collected data was consolidated and used for the result part. It will be an empirical study. The software SPSS was used for consolidating the data. In the rural area, an intervention programme was conducted by the principal investigator through an environmental hygienic education training programme. The households were selected based on the exclusion and inclusion criteria. Women who are willing to participate in the awareness programme were taken as inclusion criteria and members who are not willing to participate males and children and physically and mentally disturbed persons were excluded from this study. The study was conducted at Eazhunagarkudiruppu, Kallukkatti,

Kanchipuram district in Tamil Nadu. Women in the selected households were the respondents of this present study. The education programme “Intervention – Creating Awareness on Environmental Hygiene” was conducted for five consecutive days to promote environmental hygiene. A structured questionnaire was prepared and given to the participants based on knowledge, practices, and attitudes towards environmental sanitation. The pre and post-evaluation of the environmental hygienic perspective among the participants was done by providing the structured questionnaire on the previously mentioned basis. The following initiatives were taken to implement environmental sanitation and their importance to the people in the rural area.

1. Demonstrations using charts, posters, pamphlets, exhibitions, and live demonstrations
2. Guest lectures
3. Subject expert speakers
4. Invited physicians and medical representatives

These methods prove effective in reaching women.

Results and Discussion

Environmental hygienic practices are a pressing need in various rural places in our country. In this regard, “Intervention – Creating Awareness on Environmental Hygiene” was conducted to educate 500 households by the investigator in the rural area and various aspects were covered to educate them about environmental sanitation. On the whole, the parameter on attitude, knowledge, and practices of 500 households was evaluated before and after the programme.

Socio-demographic Profile of the Selected Households

Social demography refers to the characteristics of the population (Yang et al., pg. 2452, 2023). It deals with questions of population composition and change and how they interact with sociological variables at the individual and contextual levels. Social demography also uses demographic approaches and methods to make sense of social, economic, and political phenomena (Smock and Schwartz, pg.10, 2020). The demographic variables that were considered for analysis in this study are as follows: age, type, size of the family, education, occupation, family income, and family monthly health check-up of the respondents. Table 1 and 2 explains the socio-demographic profile of the selected households in the rural area of Eazhunagarkudiruppu, Kallukkatti, Chengalpattu, Tamil Nadu.

Table 1: Age, Educational Qualification, and Occupational Status of Selected Households

N = 500

S. No	Category	Classification	Head of Family	%	Home Maker	%
1.	Age (in years)	21-25	4	1	75	15
		26-30	67	13	92	18
		>=31	429	86	333	67
2.	Education	Illiterate	189	38	131	26
		Primary	62	12	72	14

		Secondary	181	36	204	41
		High secondary	23	5	44	9
		Graduate	8	2	8	2
		Postgraduate	31	6	34	7
		Diploma	6	1	7	1
3.	Occupational Status	Agriculture	49	10	20	4
		Daily labourer	344	69	66	13
		Homemaker	0	0	209	42
		Maid /Cook	32	6	160	32
		Self-employed	75	15	45	9

Among the selected households, the majority 86 percent of the family heads and 67 percent of homemakers belonged to the age group greater than 31 years. Educational backgrounds have had an impact on economic status and on, the lifestyle of an individual. Lifestyle changes have effects on health. The analysis of the educational status of the respondents shows that the majority of 38 percent of heads of family were illiterate, whereas 41 percent of homemakers and 36 percent of heads of the family had completed their secondary education. It was clearly stated that eight percent of both heads of family and homemakers had completed their graduation, six percent of the heads of the family, and seven percent of homemakers were postgraduates. The occupation of the respondents was also analyzed and presented in the above table. The majority of 69 percent of men and only 13 percent of women were working as daily labourers, and the majority of 42 percent of women were homemakers, and none of the men was homemakers. Similarly, 150 households were selected for the study from six hamlets. All those who were approached gave consent to participate (Aларcon Falconi 29–36.)

Image 1: Family Details and Regular Health Checkups of Selected Households

A joint family is a type of extended family composed of parents, their children, and the children's spouses and offspring in one household. Irrespective, a majority of 87 percent

of them belong to the nuclear family. A maximum of 76 percent of respondents were living in a small family (1-4) size and 18 percent of respondents were living in a medium family (4-6) and only five percent of respondents belonged to a large family (6 and above).

Regarding the number of children of the respondents, 48 percent have two children, 22 percent with one child, 14 percent don't have children, 13 percent have three children and three percent have more than four children. The age details of the children were also studied. The respondents have children of all ages. 21 percent are under the age of 5, 22 percent are between the ages of 6 and 10, 19 percent are between the ages of 11 and 15, 20 percent are between the ages of 16 and 20, and 19 percent are 21 and older. The number of respondents who have regular medical checkups or not is also studied. 33 percent of respondents are under regular health check-ups, and 67 percent of respondents are not under regular health check-ups. Regarding family income, 57 percent of the respondent's family income is between Rs. 5,000 and Rs. 10,000/-. 21 percent of respondents have a family income less than or equal to Rs.5,000, 11 percent have a family income in the range of Rs. 10,001 to Rs. 15,000, 6 percent have a family income above Rs.20,001.

Questionnaires, interviews, discussions, and analyses were used as tools to collect the empirical data (Mketoe et al.68-72). Community participation plays a vital role in health or environmental-related projects. A total of 100 people from Tanzania were engaged in an environmental-health-related study.

Effectiveness of Intervention Programme Among Selected Women

Intervention is an intentional action (singular or collective) designed for an individual, a community, or a region that alters behaviour, reduces risk, or improves outcomes (Foell et al., pg.750, 2020). Interventions can include medical or behavioural therapy, natural or built environment modification, engineering controls, public health policy, public health programmes, health communication, or public health law (Tzenios et al., pg.124, 2022). Effectiveness refers to the intervention's ability to do more good than harm for the target population in a real-world setting

Outcomes and impacts are the results of public health interventions, including effects that people experience and care about, such as a change in the ability to function, improved health, quality of life, satisfaction, or cost. A comparison of the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of respondents on environmental hygiene was conducted. Subsequently, the effectiveness of the intervention program implemented among select women on environmental hygiene was assessed and presented under the following headings:

- 1. Relationship of knowledge scores with attitudes and practices in environmental hygiene**
- 2. Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents' knowledge, attitudes, and practices on environmental hygiene.**

Comparison of Selected Women's Knowledge of Environmental Hygiene

Knowledge is the fact or condition of knowing something through familiarity gained through experience or association. Knowledge makes it easy to solve the problem and helps enhance the ability to think diversely. Hence, it is essential to identify the level of knowledge possessed by the respondents before and after the training programme (Table 3)

Table 2: Comparison of Selected Women's Knowledge of Environmental Hygiene

N = 500

Variable	Impact of Intervention	Mean	SD	t value	p-value
Knowledge of environmental hygiene	Before	4.57	1.602	27.69	0.000**
	After	10.23	4.422		

** p<0.01 level

Daily bathing is one aspect of personal hygiene knowledge that includes washing the hands with soap after going to the toilet, brushing the teeth twice a day, and covering the mouth and nose when sneezing or coughing. The interior hygiene, such as keeping living areas, food preparation areas, bathrooms, and bedrooms clean and comfortable, as well as efficiently cleaning laundry items, and the exterior environment, such as waste management practices were analyzed before and after the awareness. The result showed that there was a significant difference after the training programme (27.96) due to the effectiveness of the education programme and also the involvement and keenness of the respondents to learn and change their environmental conditions.

Similarly, cognitive interviews in correlation to sanitation and hygienic practices have been conducted with women participants from the area of Tiruchirapalli, India. This analysis highlighted the importance of sanitation-related decisions that must start with women of our nation and they also valued sanitation practices for a good hygienic environment (Doma *et al.*, pg. 3, 2023).

Comparison of Selected Women's Attitude Toward Environmental Hygiene

Attitude is a mental position about a fact or state. Attitude is the basis for everything and determines how we react to adversity, grow and learn, overcome challenges, and create bonds with others. Table 4 explains the practices of environmental hygiene before and after the education programme.

Table 3: Comparison of respondent's attitudes toward environmental hygiene

N = 500

Variable	Impact of Intervention	Mean	SD	t value	p-value
Attitudes on environmental hygiene	Before	30.15	3.663	9.303	0.000**
	After	32.85	5.964		

** p<0.01 level

The findings suggest that enhancing hygienic attitudes may play an important role in promoting hygienic behaviour among the selected households. A hygienic education programme in connection with preventive health examinations might also contribute to activating hygienic-promoting behaviour. Hence, in the aspect of attitude towards hygiene, there was a significant difference (9.303) found after the intervention.

A community-based cross-sectional study has been conducted with 422 participants from Ethiopia by random sampling technique. The knowledge, attitude, and practice associated with wastewater management were analyzed in the selected area. Various factors

such as house rent and civil servants were associated with the knowledge of the participants while good knowledge and space availability were connected with the attitude of the participants and the positive attitude was in connection with the good practice of the selected participants. Limited knowledge, attitude, and practice were observed in the participants. Hygienic interventions are largely needed (Kabito *et al.*, 2022). Studies done in Dharmapuri and Chennai also pointed out the need for knowledge-based intervention programmes to sort out and solve them among rural women.

Comparison of Household Practices on Environmental Hygiene

Environmental hygiene includes the use of safe drinking water, personal hygiene, proper refuse, and liquid waste management, provision of food safety, and healthful housing the practice of environmental hygiene before and after the training programme was assessed. The statistical difference in the practice of environmental hygiene is represented in Table 5.

Table 4: Comparison of household practices on environmental hygiene

N = 500

Variable	Impact of intervention	Mean	SD	t value	p-value
Practices of environmental hygiene	Before	14.26	2.653	20.277	0.000**
	After	23.31	9.976		

** p<0.01 level

In the aspect of practices on health, food, and sanitation before and after the intervention, there is a significant difference (20.27) since the respondents realized the importance and role of safeguarding the interior and exterior environment to promote individual, family, community, and overall well-being of the society.

A cross-sectional and descriptive study was conducted with 135 participants with random sampling in the place of South Africa. The findings might make it easier to implement a program for knowledge improvement that incorporates a formal training curriculum and standard operating procedures. The findings of the study cannot be applied to the entire nation; thus, it is suggested that a nationwide survey of similar occurrences be taken into consideration (Thompson *et al.*, pg.6, 2022). Already studies done in India also pointed out the same suggestions.

Public health performance of sanitation technologies in Tamil Nadu, India: Initial perspectives based on *E. coli* release (Tiruchirappalli City Corporation, 2018; TNUSSP, 2018a; TNUSSP, 2017; TNUSSP, 2016). While there is a wide range of on-site sanitation technologies used in much of the world, there has been little systematic study of their relative effectiveness in reducing pathogen release in either liquid or solid waste streams, or of the combined release of pathogens to the environment from these two streams.

Relationship of Knowledge Scores with Attitudes and Practices on Environmental Hygiene before and after Intervention

The positive correlations between knowledge and attitude, knowledge and practice, and attitude and practice in this study reaffirm the relationship between knowledge, attitude, and practice with infection control measures. It is concluded that adequate knowledge can lead to a positive attitude and good practices. The relationship between environmental

hygiene before and after the program was evaluated based on knowledge, attitude, and practices. The results are summarized in Table 6.

Table 5: Relationship of Knowledge Scores With Attitude and Practices on Environmental Hygiene Before and After Intervention

N = 500

Variables	Before			After		
	Knowledge	Attitude	Practice	Knowledge	Attitude	Practice
Knowledge	1	.183**	-.002	1	.324**	.671**
Attitude	.183**	1	-.045	.324**	1	.303**
Practice	-.002	-.045	1	.671**	.303**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

Before the intervention, there was a significant positive correlation between knowledge and attitude (.183), whereas there was no significant correlation between knowledge and practice or attitude and practice. After the intervention, there is a significant positive correlation between knowledge, attitudes, and practices. The correlation between knowledge and attitude is .324, the correlation between knowledge and practice is .671, and the correlation between attitude and practice is .303. Based on the results, the positive correlations between knowledge and attitude, knowledge and practice, and attitude and practice were observed. This confirms the relationship between knowledge, attitude, and practice about infection control measures. It is concluded that adequate knowledge can result in a positive outlook and ethical conduct.

A cross-sectional study was designed to involve individuals over 18 years of age living in Thandalam village, Chennai, India. Basic information about sociodemographic profiles and existing drinking water and sanitation-related knowledge, attitudes, and practices were collected using a modified version of a previously validated questionnaire and analyzed. 45% of the participants were not following any methods of water treatment and among them, half of the participants felt that water available to them was clean and did not require any additional treatment. Twenty-five percent of the participants surveyed did not have access to toilets inside their households. There is a need for intervention to educate individuals about drinking water treatment methods, sanitation, and hand-washing practices (Kuberan *et al.*, p. 73,).

The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents' Environmental Hygiene Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice

The percentage frequency distribution, in general, is a display of data that indicates the percentage of observations for each data point or grouping of data points. It is a commonly used method for expressing the relative frequency of survey responses and other data. The frequency and percentage distribution of respondents' knowledge, attitude, and practice of environmental hygiene before and after the intervention is expressed in the relative frequency of respective aspects of environmental hygiene (Table 7).

Image 2: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents' Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice of Environmental Hygiene Before and After Intervention

In the pre-test, 25 percent of respondents had poor knowledge, the majority (55 percent) of them had fair knowledge, and only 20 percent had good knowledge. In the post-test, the majority (71 percent) of respondents had good knowledge, 20 percent had fair knowledge, and the number of people in the poor category decreased to nine percent. 32 percent of respondents had poor attitudes, 45 percent had fair attitudes, and 23 percent had good attitudes. In the post-test, the number of respondents with poor attitudes decreased to 21 percent. Forty percent and 39 percent of respondents had fair and good attitudes, respectively. 26 percent of respondents had poor practices, 36 percent had fair practices and only 18 percent had good practices about environmental hygiene. In the post-test, the number of respondents with good practices increased from 18 percent to 54 percent. The result of the study showed that, before the intervention, only a limited number of respondents were aware of environmental hygiene, but after the intervention, more than 55 percent of the respondents were practising good hygienic practices. Findings suggest that the intervention program played a significant role in elevating the overall lifestyle of the targeted individuals. They also learnt lots of hygienic skills and practising nowadays. They were very much interested in developing their needs and fulfilment.

Conclusion

Overpopulation, poverty, illiteracy, a lack of understanding, and unfit environments are accelerating environmental degradation. Hence, the research showed that educating people on good environmental hygiene practices is a powerful means of inspiring them to take action for the planet's future. More environmental education is needed to provide community groups and individuals with a foundational knowledge of the environment and its related challenges. Indeed, repeated hygiene promotion programmes are recommended for rural people to play active roles in the promotion of sanitation and hygienic practices. With women as a target group for health and hygiene education, sanitation promotion programmes could be able to reach other women at home in their areas and address and respond to their

needs and problems. Indeed, the intervention program “Intervention – Creating Awareness on Environmental Hygiene” has proven highly effective in transforming environmental hygiene knowledge, attitudes, and practices among participants. Positive changes in personal hygiene, household cleanliness, and waste management underscore the program's tangible impact. Targeting participants above 30 years and recognizing the influence of educational backgrounds on socio-economic status highlights its inclusive approach. Tailored interventions for daily labourers and the pivotal role of homemakers demonstrate adaptability. The prevalence of nuclear families emphasizes the need for family-focused strategies, accommodating varying family sizes. Improved KAP, positive attitude shifts, and correlated practices collectively affirm the program's success, reflected in a significant shift from poor to good outcomes post-intervention. This comprehensive approach sets a promising precedent for future health interventions.

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Appendix

Environmental hygiene: Environmental health corresponds to behaviours, practices, and attitudes that are aimed at protecting individuals from infections caused by poor sanitary practices and conditions. Examples of common sources of poor sanitary conditions are unhygienic water, lack of access to private toilets, poor water and waste disposal systems, public defecation and urination, poor hand-wash practices, unhygienic food sources, and unhygienic housing.

Socio-Demographic Questionnaire

Name : _____

Age (in years): _____

1. Education Level:

- Illiterate
- Elementary School
- Middle School
- High School
- Diploma
- Undergraduate
- Post-Graduate

2. Occupation:

- Homemaker
- Cook
- Maid
- Daily labourer
- Masonry
- Agriculture
- Self-Employed
- Others, please specify: _____

3. Family Monthly Income Level:

- ≤ 5,000 INR
- 5,001-10,000 INR
- 10,001 – 15,000 INR
- 15,001 – 20,000 INR
- > 20,001 INR

4. Head of the Family:

- Husband
- Father-in-law
- Mother-in-law

- My mother
- My father
- Me – Wife/Mother

5. Age of Husband:

- ≤ 20
- 21-25
- 26-30
- ≥ 31

6. Education of Husband:

- Illiterate
- Diploma
- Secondary School
- High School
- Under Graduation

7. Occupation of the Husband:

- Daily labourer
- Masonry
- Agriculture
- Self-Employed
- Others, please specify: _____

8. Number of Children:

- No children
- 1
- 2
- 3
- More than 4

9. Age of Children

- ≤ 5
- 6-10
- 11-15
- 16-20
- ≥ 21

10. Family Type:

- Joint family
- Nuclear family

11. Number of Family Members Living at Home:

- 1
 2
 3
 4
 5
 6
 ≥ 7

12. Do you go for a health check-up regularly?

- Yes
 No

Self-Developed Health, Food, and Sanitation Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) Questionnaire

Knowledge about Health, Food, and Sanitation

1. Are you aware of the harmful effects of incorrectly disposing the waste on the environment and health?

- Yes
 No
 I do not know

2. Burning garbage has harmful effects on the environment.

- Yes
 No
 Sometimes
 I do not know

3. It Is not a good practice to bury waste such as plastic, glass, and paper outside.

- Yes
 No
 I do not know

4. There are natural ways of promoting food waste decomposition.

- Yes
 No
 I do not know

5. Waste materials should be segregated into wet waste (food items) and dry waste (plastic, metal, and paper materials)

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

6. Do you think the quality of water affects your health?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes

7. What are some health issues you think are caused by poor water quality?

- Dysentery
- Cholera
- Diarrheal
- Hepatitis A
- Typhoid
- I do not know

8. Do you know the importance of washing your hands?

- Yes
- No

9. Washing hands without soap after using the toilet is not good.

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

10. It is not good to let water stagnate in areas around and outside the house.

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

11. It is important to store drinking water in covered containers.

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

12. What are some health issues caused by faecal to oral and soil to oral contact?

- Hepatitis A/E
- Typhoid
- Cholera
- Common cold
- Tapeworms

- Poliovirus
- I do not know

13. Public defecation and urination has negative effects on those living in and around the area.

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

14. Does animal dung result in diseases?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

15. Source of information regarding sanitation and hygiene?

- Television
- Social media
- Radio
- Neighbours
- Medical professions
- Non-governmental organizations
- Village initiatives
- Family members/relatives
- If others, please specify: _____

Attitudes about Health, Food, and Sanitation

16. It is each individual's responsibility to dispose waste in dustbins.

- Agree
- Somewhat agree
- Disagree

17. Defecating/urinating in public is very convenient.

- Agree
- Somewhat agree
- Disagree

18. Not cleaning utensils for many days is unhygienic.

- Agree
- Somewhat agree
- Disagree

19. Washing hands before and after eating is a waste of time.

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- Agree
- Somewhat agree
- Disagree

20. Washing hands after using the toilet is not effective in preventing diseases.

- Agree
- Somewhat agree
- Disagree

21. The actions of one person in environmental sanitation is not sufficient.

- Agree
- Somewhat agree
- Disagree

22. Proper sanitation practices are expensive.

- Agree
- Somewhat agree
- Disagree

23. It is important to practice good sanitation and hygiene and be a role model to our children.

- Agree
- Somewhat agree
- Disagree

24. Wastewater should be disposed of in an appropriate manner.

- Agree
- Somewhat agree
- Disagree

25. Bathing is essential for hygiene purposes and not only beauty purposes.

- Agree
- Somewhat agree
- Disagree

26. The hands of family members will not cause a problem even if it is unhygienic.

- Agree
- Somewhat agree
- Disagree

27. It is not proper to share drinking cups with others.

- Agree
- Somewhat agree
- Disagree

28. Proper sanitary practices are the way to prevent many infections.

- Agree
- Somewhat agree
- Disagree

29. Individual toilets are only important for privacy and not hygiene purposes.

- Agree
- Somewhat agree
- Disagree

30. It is not necessary that hands are washed with soap.

- Agree
- Somewhat agree
- Disagree

Practices about Health, Food, and Sanitation

31. Do you burn waste in the open?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Most of the time
- All the time

32. Do you dispose the waste in an open area?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Most of the time
- All the time

33. Do you dispose the waste in a community dustbin?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Most of the time
- All the time

34. Do you separate your waste by recyclable and non-recyclable products?

- Never
- Sometimes

- Most of the time
- All the time

35. Do you have difficulties in procuring clean water?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Most of the time
- All the time

36. Do you have access to clean drinking water?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Most of the time
- All the time

37. Do you wash your hands before and after eating?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Most of the time
- All the time

38. Do you have access to a toilet at home?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Most of the time
- All the time

39. Are there public toilets in the area?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Most of the time
- All the time

40. Are the toilets clean at your house?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Most of the time
- All the time

41. Are the toilets in public clean?

- Never
- Sometimes

- Most of the time
- All the time

42. Is there access to water in the toilets?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Most of the time
- All the time

43. Do you defecate or urinate in public spaces?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Most of the time
- All the time

44. Do you wash your hands after using the toilet?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Most of the time
- All the time

45. Do you wash your hands after coming back home?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Most of the time
- All the time

Note: The questionnaire can be reused with proper attribution to the author.